

SURVEY OF FETEL HEART MONITONING SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

This research is designed in alignment with recent reports published by World Health Organization (WHO) on Congenital heart diseases (CHD) the most common heart problem and the possible detection methods. Recent estimates show that 2.1 million individuals are suffering from CHD in 2020 out of which 29% of them suffer death as an average in the world every year due to cardiac trauma. Third world countries with low and moderate incomes are affected adversely at 35% of death caused by CHD occurs in these countries out of the world total numbers irrespective of gender. It is estimated to be about 3,06,000 in 2030 individuals would suffer from heart diseases.

Southeast Asia and Indian region is the most prominent areas of concern because of changes of life styles, food habits, and occupational culture. Fetal Heart Diseases (FHD) mainly affect individuals with 2 months old and older but still expanding in developing countries due to lack of health care in these countries. The recent reports of WHO also indicates, the need for accurate methods for

prediction at early stage by efficient periodical examination of heart to diagnose heart diseases are very crucial for health care planning of such countries. The number and size of medical databases are rapidly increasing, and the advanced models of data mining techniques could help physicians to make efficient and applicable decisions. The challenges of FHD data include the feature selection, the number of the samples; imbalance of the samples, lack of magnitude for some features, etc. This study mainly focuses on the feature selection improvement and decreasing the numbers of the features. In this study, meta-heuristic approach is suggested in order to select prominent features of the FHD.

Keywords : *FHD, CHD, Analysis, Image Processing.*

1. INTRODUCTION

The heart is important organ of human body part. It is nothing more than a pump, which pumps blood through the body. If circulation of blood in body is inefficient the organs like brain suffer and if heart stops working altogether, death occurs within minutes. Medical diagnosis of heart related

disorders is a complicated task but extremely important task that should be performed accurately and efficiently in a group of patients looking for control of FHD based diseases. As human life is completely dependent on proficient working of the heart, the term Heart disease refers to disease of heart & blood vessel system and it is a major cause of morbidity and mortality in the modern society.

Early detection of heart disease is curable easy to reduce the mortality rate. The traditional way of predicting heart disease is doctor's examination involves number of medical tests including ultrasound scan, Cardiocography (CTG) of heart test on individual. Most of the times this manual detection is time consuming and needs opinion of a specialist physician for a substantial number of times on visit of the patient. Any minor symptomatic signals sent by the heart to the patient during the normal course of action of the individual and only knowledge based inference can be made on the part of the patient.

To reduce the mishaps based on this problem computer aided expert systems have been developed for predicting FHD, a lot of automatic FHD classification methods are available but not able to give clear indication of confirmatory No or Yes to the expert physician with required levels of accuracy. Hence it is felt that based on the detailed literature survey and practical case study we are going to conclude which one is best for the identification of FHD.

The accurate modality required to be developed for detection, pattern matching, prediction and image processing for presentation to the second opinion. The detailed technical background of the research work is presented in this paper, for the survey of detection and prediction of FHD.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

The detailed literature survey is carried out to get an idea and fact ascertained on the state of the art of expert systems that are being in use for the assistance of the practicing professionals. The related literature from various journals were collected and classified into relevant literature with expert systems and data driven systems for prediction and alert systems. The different methods and computerized tools algorithms adopted were also taken into account for literature review to give broader outlook of the problem. The extensive literature has reports on enormous ways and means to reach out on the solutions as localized, individualistic, trial based, tailor made, system specific models to reach the conclusive support for the human health system monitoring and alert system. In the end the literature has given the research a completely thought provoking inference to develop most suited and user friendly hybrid algorithm based solution that accommodates patent alert system. The Streptococcal infection in the valves of the heart creates damages in soft portions of the heart, which results in disease. Generally an

abnormal immune response is the simple result when administered by trained physician to a group of patients usually during the treatment.

Fetal congenital heart disease (FHD) is a common and serious congenital malformation in children [1]. In Asia, FHD birth defect rates have reached as high as 9.3%. For the early detection of birth defects and mortality, echocardiography remains the most effective method for screening fetal heart malformations. However, standard echocardiograms of the fetal heart, especially four-chamber view images, are difficult to obtain. In addition, the pathophysiological changes in fetal hearts during different pregnancy periods lead to ever-changing two-dimensional fetal heart structures and hemodynamics, and it requires extensive professional knowledge to recognize and judge disease development. Thus, research on the automatic screening for FHD is necessary. In this paper, we proposed a new model named DGACNN that shows the best performance in recognizing FHD, achieving a rate of 85%. The motivation for this network is to deal with the problem that there are insufficient training datasets to train a robust model. There are many unlabeled video slices, but they are tough and time-consuming to annotate. Thus, how to use these un-annotated video slices to improve the DGACNN capability for recognizing FHD, in terms of both recognition accuracy and robustness, is very meaningful for FHD screening. The architecture of DGACNN

comprises two parts, that is, DANomaly and GACNN (Wgan-GP and CNN). DANomaly, similar to the ALOCC network, but incorporates cycle adversarial learning to train an end-to-end one-class classification (OCC) network that is more robust and has a higher accuracy than ALOCC in screening video slices. For the GACNN architecture, we use FCH (four chamber heart) video slices at around the end-systole, as screened by DANomaly, to train a WGAN-GP for the purpose of obtaining ideal low-level features that can robustly improve the FHD recognition accuracy. A few annotated video slices, as screened by DANomaly, can also be used for data augmentation so as to improve the FHD recognition further. The experiments show that the DGACNN outperforms other state-of-the-art networks by 1%-20% in recognizing FHD. A comparison experiment shows that the proposed network already outperforms the performance of expert cardiologists in recognizing FHD, reaching 84% in a test. Thus, the proposed architecture has high potential for helping cardiologists complete early FHD screenings.

The separation tool of Fetal [2] ECG is complicated and very important in medical diagnosis during pregnancy. This work proposes the separation and enhanced classification of fetal ECG signals from abdominal ECG signals to find heart diseases of the fetal. In this paper MULTI-COMBI based

blind source separation technique is used to separate the fetal ECG signals. The separated ECG signals have different features, which are extracted using the morphological feature extraction method. These extracted features are used for classification by Enhanced Navie Bayes Classification technique. This classifier classified into five different classes of disease. The entire work is implemented in MATLAB. The Simulated results of BSS method gives low PSNR and SIR values and the enhanced classifier gives the accuracy as 96.56%, Sensitivity as 89.56%, and Specificity as 97.54%.

Congenital heart disease (CHD) is one of the main problems that can occur during pregnancy [3]. Annually, 300,000 babies die during pregnancy or infancy because of CHD. Early detection of CHD leads to reduced mortality and morbidity, but is hampered by the relatively low detection rates (i.e. < 60%) of current CHD screening technology. This detection rate could be improved by complementing echocardiographic screening with assessment of the fetal electrocardiogram (ECG). In this study, the fetal ECG was measured non-invasively, with electrodes on the maternal abdomen, in almost 400 fetuses, 30% of which had known CHD. The fetal ECG measurements were processed to yield a 3-dimensional fetal vectorcardiogram. A deep neural network was trained to classify this fetal vectorcardiogram as either originating from a

healthy fetus or CHD. The network was evaluated on a test set of about 100 patients, showing a CHD detection accuracy of 76%. Non-invasive fetal electrocardiography therefore shows clear potential in diagnosis of CHD and should be considered as supplementary technology next to echocardiography.

Fetal echocardiography uses ultrasound technique to view of the baby even when the baby is in the mother's womb [4]. Obstetricians refer the patients to undergo this procedure if they find any suspicious conditions of having defects in the fetal heart. This test is done usually during 2nd trimester. Fetal ultrasound measurements are one of the most important factors for high quality obstetrics health care in order to estimate the Gestational age, exact delivery date and growth of the fetus. The standard 2D ultrasound imaging technique examines the fetal heart in different views. The information related to the cardiac size, structure, rhythm and movement can be obtained in four chamber view. Various congenital defects can be visualized by the examination of fetal cardiac chambers. It is very difficult to locate the cardiac chambers and do the relevant measurement, hence it is challenging work to researchers of biomedical community. A semi automated method of segmentation has been proposed in this experimental study to segment the fetal heart chambers using Possibilistic c-means clustering

technique. The Ultrasonic images of fetal heart having four - chambers in apical view was used in order to do the study with simulation. The input fetal cardiac frame was denoised and enhanced. The enhancement of the input image was carried out by converting it in to gray image. This was then converted to binarized image. On the selected chambers the region growing technique followed by PCM was used to segment the cardiac chambers. Finally the region properties were used to measure the ventricles that is the left ventricle and right ventricle of the fetal heart and LV/RV estimation is done based on standard values. The ratio of the width of left ventricle and right ventricle were calculated which closely matched with the theoretical width considered as the standard for different gestation week. The proposed semi - automated technique need to be validated before being used for assessment as the clinical tool by large datasets.

Despite the enormous potential applications, non-invasive recordings have not yet made enough satisfaction for fetal disease detection [5] . This is mainly due to the fetal ECG signal is contaminated by the maternal electrocardiograph (ECG) interference, muscle contractions, and motion artifacts. In this paper, we propose a joint multiple subspace-based blind source separation (BSS) approach to extract the fetal heart rate (HR), so that it could greatly reduce the effect of maternal ECG and motion artifacts. The approach relies on the

estimation of the coefficient matrix formulated as the tensor decomposition in terms of multiple datasets. Since the objective function takes the coupling information from the stacking of the covariance matrix for multiple datasets into account, estimating the coefficient matrices is fulfilled not only on dependence across multiple datasets, but also can combine the extracted components across four different datasets. Numerical results demonstrate that the proposed method can achieve a high extracted HR accuracy for each dataset, when compared to some conventional methods.

Congenital Heart Disease is a blemish in the structure of heart and its great vessels for the prenatal [6]. Clear monitoring of the infant in utero from gestation to labour still remains a big challenge. Measurement of fetal Electrocardiogram is a low cost non invasive method by placing the electrode on the abdominal skin of mother. This abdominal electrocardiogram consists of fetal electrocardiogram along with the interferences like mother ECG and other noises. The proposed system focuses on the detection of R-peaks in fetal electrocardiogram signal. Savitzky Golay filter in conjunction with wavelet transform is used for denoising and extracting the mECG signal. Fuzzy C means clustering tool groups the R-peaks of fetal electrocardiogram signal. The obtained waveform reveals the heart rate of both fetus and mother which can be used for further

diagnosis purpose. A good quality of R-peaks is detected for the extracted fetal electrocardiogram is evident from signal to noise ratio of 40.3807 dB.

Accurate screening for septal defects is important for supporting radiologists' interpretative work [7]. Some previous studies have proposed semantic segmentation and object detection approaches to carry out fetal heart detection; unfortunately, the models could not segment different objects of the same class. The semantic segmentation method segregates regions that only contain objects from the same class. In contrast, the fetal heart may contain multiple objects, such as the atria, ventricles, valves, and aorta. Besides, blurry boundaries (shadows) or a lack of consistency in the acquisition ultrasonography can cause wide variations. This study utilizes Mask-RCNN (MRCNN) to handle fetal ultrasonography images and employ it to detect and segment defects in heart walls with multiple objects. To our knowledge, this is the first study involving a medical application for septal defect detection using instance segmentation. The use of MRCNN architecture with ResNet50 as a backbone and a 0.0001 learning rate allows for two times faster training of the model on fetal heart images compared to other object detection methods, such as Faster-RCNN (FRCNN). We demonstrate a strong correlation between the predicted septal defects and ground truth as a mean average precision (mAP). As shown in

the results, the proposed MRCNN model achieves good performance in multiclass detection of the heart chamber, with 97.59% for the right atrium, 99.67% for the left atrium, 86.17% for the left ventricle, 98.83% for the right ventricle, and 99.97% for the aorta. We also report competitive results for the defect detection of holes in the atria and ventricles via semantic and instance segmentation. The results show that the mAP for MRCNN is about 99.48% and 82% for FRCNN. We suggest that evaluation and prediction with our proposed model provide reliable detection of septal defects, including defects in the atria, ventricles, or both. These results suggest that the model used has a high potential to help cardiologists complete the initial screening for fetal congenital heart disease.

Automatic detection of fetal ECG features [8] can assist in diagnosis of fetal cardiac complications and may reduce the time required for diagnosis. Detection of the end of the repolarization period wave in ECG has been proven challenging due to its low amplitude and low frequency range. The prolongation of end of T-wave is associated with sudden cardiac death, thus, methods that can accurately pinpoint it is highly desirable for early diagnosis of cardiac diseases. In this paper, a technique based on recurrence plots is developed for the detection of end of T-wave. The developed technique was tested on maternal ECG (mECG), fetal scalp ECG

(fsECG) and non-invasive fetal ECG (nfECG) records. The technique was able to detect end of T-waves in all of the mECG beats, 75% of the non-invasive fECG beats (verified by simultaneously captured doppler ultrasound signals) and 78% of the fsECG beats. Detection of fECG signals were more challenging than mECG signals due to the noise and their low amplitude T-waves.

Fetal magnetoencephalography (fMEG) is a method to record human fetal brain signals in pregnant mothers [9]. Nevertheless the amplitude of the fetal brain signal is very small and the fetal brain signal is overlaid by interfering signals mainly caused by maternal and fetal heart activity. Several methods are used to attenuate the interfering signals for the extraction of the fetal brain signal. However currently used methods are often affected by a reduction of the fetal brain signal or redistribution of the fetal brain signal. To overcome this limitation we developed a new fully automated procedure for removal of heart activity (FAUNA) based on Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and Ridge Regression. We compared the results with an orthogonal projection (OP) algorithm which is widely used in fetal research. The analysis was performed on simulated data sets containing spontaneous and averaged brain activity. The new analysis was able to extract fetal brain signals with an increased signal to noise ratio and without redistribution of activity across

sensors compared to OP. The attenuation of interfering heart signals in fMEG data was significantly improved by FAUNA and supports fully automated evaluation of fetal brain signal.

Fetal ECG monitoring has become important as it helps to detect the abnormalities in child during pregnancy [10]. The prior knowledge about the fetal health could help in reducing complications and maintaining good and healthy pregnancy. FEECG is contaminated by many external factors so its extraction becomes little complicated. FEECG is used to examine the structure and functioning of baby's heart. It helps us to identify and diagnose congenital heart defects before birth. The total nine months of pregnancy is divided into three trimesters. During each trimester, the fetus grows and develops to the next stage. A test will be done on each trimester to detect birth defects, identify correct some kinds of fetal problems that may affect child birth. This paper performs some research explorations on various techniques and algorithms used for the extraction of Fetal ECG from Maternal ECG.

The characterization of the fetal cardiac cycle [11] is an important determination of fetal health and stress. The anomalous appearance of different anatomical structures during different phases of the heart cycle is a key indicator of fetal congenital heart disease. However, locating the fetal heart using ultrasound is challenging, as the heart is small and indistinct.

In this paper, we present a viewpoint agnostic solution that automatically characterizes the cardiac cycle in clinical ultrasound scans of the fetal heart. When estimating the state of the cardiac cycle, our model achieves a mean-squared error of 0.177 between the ground truth cardiac cycle and our prediction. We also show that our network is able to localize the heart, despite the lack of labels indicating the location of the heart in the training process.

3. CONCLUSION

This paper deals with the study of the different existing methodologies for classifying the FHD. In recent years, many new classification algorithms are proposed but there is no distinct best algorithm that is successful in all aspects. Optimization approaches are also applied for classifying the FHD datasets.

4. REFERENCES

1. Y. Gong et al., "Fetal Congenital Heart Disease Echocardiogram Screening Based on DGACNN: Adversarial One-Class Classification Combined with Video Transfer Learning," in *IEEE Transactions on Medical Imaging*, vol. 39, no. 4, pp. 1206-1222, April 2020, doi: 10.1109/TMI.2019.2946059.
2. X. F. Joseph, A. T. Waktola, D. Senay and S. R. Breesha, "An Enhanced Classification Technique for Fetal ECG Signal Separation to Diagnose Fetal Heart Diseases," 2019 *IEEE International Conference on Intelligent Techniques in Control, Optimization and Signal Processing (INCOS)*, 2019, pp. 1-5, doi: 10.1109/INCOS45849.2019.8951317.
3. R. Vullings, "Fetal Electrocardiography and Deep Learning for Prenatal Detection of Congenital Heart Disease," 2019 *Computing in Cardiology (CinC)*, 2019, pp. Page 1-Page 4, doi: 10.23919/CinC49843.2019.9005870.
4. P. Prabha V., N. Sriraam and S. Suresh, "Hybrid Segmentation Approach to Segment Fetal Cardiac Chambers of Ultrasound images," 2019 1st *International Conference on Advanced Technologies in Intelligent Control, Environment, Computing & Communication Engineering (ICATIECE)*, 2019, pp. 331-334, doi: 10.1109/ICATIECE45860.2019.9063777.
5. L. Wang, T. Ohtsuki, K. Owada, N. Honma and H. Hayashi, "Joint Multiple Subspace-based BSS Method for Fetal Heart Rate Extraction from Non-invasive Recordings," 2020 42nd *Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine & Biology Society (EMBC)*, 2020, pp. 616-620, doi: 10.1109/EMBC44109.2020.9175307.

6. S. M. and I. J. S., "Analysis of R - PEAKS in Fetal Electrocardiogram to Detect Heart Disorder using Fuzzy Clustering," 2019 IEEE 5th International Conference for Convergence in Technology (I2CT), 2019, pp. 1-4, doi: 10.1109/I2CT45611.2019.9033732.
7. S. Nurmaini et al., "Accurate Detection of Septal Defects With Fetal Ultrasonography Images Using Deep Learning-Based Multiclass Instance Segmentation," in IEEE Access, vol. 8, pp. 196160-196174, 2020, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2020.3034367.
8. N. Widatalla, A. Khandoker, Y. Kasahara and Y. Kimura, "Detection of End of T-wave in Fetal ECG Using Recurrence Plots," 2019 41st Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society (EMBC), 2019, pp. 2618-2621, doi: 10.1109/EMBC.2019.8856737.
9. K. Sippel et al., "Fully Automated Subtraction of Heart Activity for Fetal Magnetoencephalography Data*," 2019 41st Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society (EMBC), 2019, pp. 5685-5689, doi: 10.1109/EMBC.2019.8856603.
10. R. Raut, A. Dikshit-Ratnaparkhi and D. Bormane, "Development of Algorithm for Extraction of Fetal from Maternal ECG on Benchmark Database and rototype Development for Acquisition," 2020 Fourth International Conference on Computing Methodologies and Communication (ICCMC), 2020, pp. 315-318, doi: 10.1109/ICCMC48092.2020.ICCMC-00059.
11. L. H. Lee and J. A. Noble, "Automatic Determination of the Fetal Cardiac Cycle in Ultrasound Using Spatio-Temporal Neural Networks," 2020 IEEE 17th International Symposium on Biomedical Imaging (ISBI), 2020, pp. 1937-1940, doi: 10.1109/ISBI45749.2020.9098613.